

Interaction of climate and soil pH in determining crop resilience and quality

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Introduction

- The impacts of climate change on yields and crop quality are moderated by land management practices
- Soil pH plays a crucial role in nutrient cycling
 - maintaining the soil at the optimum pH is critical for maximising yield

Methods

- Trial established in 1961 in North Scotland to demonstrate impact of soil pH on yield to farmers

- 8 course ley / arable rotation
- Yields measured every year

- Fitted gaussian curve to for each year for the oats & estimated the asymptotic maximum yield
- Random Forest Regression used to identify key weather parameters

Results - Yield

- Spring barley yields – not tolerant of low pH but tolerant of high pH

- Spring oats yields – tolerant of low pH but not tolerant of high pH

Spring oats yields per cycle - Box and whisker plots show median, min, max and interquartile range

Ten most important weather variables influencing the asymptotic maximum yield

Season Oct-Sept

rain = total precipitation (mm)

rain_intensity = rain / (number of days rain > 1.0 mm)

rain_flag = number of days rain > 1.0 mm

Med_rain_flag = number of days rain > 1 & rain <= 10

Drought_flag = number days where daily rainfall <= 0.3mm

Drought = max number of consecutive drought days per period

- Grain N%
 - Spring oats – median stable with pH
 - Winter wheat & spring barley – median increases with pH

Conclusions

- Asymptotic maximum yield impacted by weather
- pH impacts grain N%
- Grain N yield – impacted by both pH and weather

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